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[Alternatives]

The Contested Futures of Just Transition in Canada's Energy Sector

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Abstract

The Government of Canada's long-awaited just transition legislation (termed the "Sustainable Jobs Act") recently passed through the House of Commons. However, the future of this policy is contested, especially within Alberta's oil and gas sector. Here we identify four distinct discourses of just transition based on a textual analysis of public, corporate, and civil society rhetoric. We argue the Sustainable Jobs Act attempts a strategic political balance by allying with labour and using discursive tactics to simultaneously appease more radical left and right perspectives. As a result, it does not substantively support meaningful climate action (or climate justice) and leaves Canadian workers at risk of forthcoming global economic shifts.

Keywords: Just Transition; Alberta; United Conservative Party; Sustainable Jobs

Introduction

In 2019, Canadian Prime Minister Justin Trudeau, then seeking re-election for a second term, announced plans to enact a Just Transition Act¹ intended to support oil and gas workers as Canada pursued its goal of Net-Zero carbon emissions by the year 2050.

Despite Trudeau's election victory, subsequent action on this file was slow and uncoordinated.² However, public interest and debate about just transition has recently resurfaced after two notable recent political events: First, Jonathan Wilkinson, Canada's Minister of Natural Resources, announced in the Spring of 2023 that new legislation was forthcoming to support a just transition.³ This legislation – nicknamed the "Sustainable Jobs Act" – eventually passed in the House of Commons in April 2024.

Second, Alberta's right populist Premier Danielle Smith secured a Majority government in the province's 2023 general elections.⁴ Alberta is at the centre of Canada's just transition debate because of its large oil and gas sector, which (along with supporting industries) employs more than 100,000 workers. The province is also responsible for over 38% of Canada's greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, despite only having 11.5% of the country's population.⁵ Smith has spoken critically of just transition, claiming that Trudeau "intends to shut down our energy industry".⁶ Her election victory complicates the Federal Government's just transition plans, as political power in Canada's dominant

oil and gas producing province has been consolidated within the hands of a vocal “anti-transitioner”.

Beyond Smith, there are a wide range of stakeholders across the Canadian political spectrum who have interpreted just transition in different ways. In this contribution, we categorize four distinct discourses of just transition in the context of Alberta’s oil and gas sector. Inspired by Hadrian Mertins-Kirkwood’s 2023 commentary on Bill C-50,⁷ we show how the current Federal approach to a just transition, embodied within its Sustainable Jobs Act,⁸ attempts to reconcile the concerns of organized labour groups while simultaneously appeasing more polarizing perspectives (such as Smith’s), albeit neglecting more ambitious and decolonial climate justice opportunities. Ultimately, this discursive battle over what just transition entails is occurring while the world is experiencing dangerous levels of global warming.⁹ Decisions made today will have important implications for Canada’s ability to comply with international climate commitments, and its capacity to insulate the domestic economy from likely economic shifts if the rest of the world pursues ambitious climate action. We argue here that while the Federal government’s approach to just transition attempts a strategic political balance, it does not substantively support meaningful climate action (or climate justice) and leaves Canadian workers vulnerable to expected forthcoming global economic shifts in the oil and gas sector. This is perhaps unsurprising given Canada’s “political and cultural hegemony” which typically “legitimizes extractivism as a desired

economic destiny,” a clear example of which is Trudeau’s “declaration that building new pipelines is in the ‘national interest;.”¹⁰ Although politicians like Trudeau and Smith may have differing views on the rate and extent of oil and gas extraction, if more progressive parties present substantial opposition to extractivism, they “will still face the full force of the settler colonial state and global capitalism.”¹¹

Assessing Competing Discourses

We employed a textual analysis of publicly available documents featuring different interpretations of the idea of just transition. Specifically, we categorized and coded 37 recent statements about just transition in the context of Alberta or Federal politics from the last 9 years from 28 different high-profile actors. These actors included politicians, environmental activists, labour representatives, journalists, and other prominent public figures in Canada. Relevant citations were analyzed to tease out different meanings and interpretations for just transition, which we grouped into four “discourses” – defined by Riedy as “invisible webs of meaning” that “contain stories and narratives that help us to make sense of our complex reality” and which “permeate media and culture, underpin economies, institutions, organizations and technological systems.”¹² Specifically, citations were assessed with respect to each perspective’s definition of justice, its stance on the role of oil and gas production and consumption within a net-

zero economy, and compatibility with other just transition interpretations (see Supplementary Data Table).

Four Just Transitions

The notion of a just transition dates back to the 1970s, when the North American labour movement first sought to protect workers' livelihoods in response to newly enacted environmental regulations which had potential impacts on industry.¹³ Today, jobs in the carbon-intensive fossil fuel industry are a primary focus of just transition discourse as governments advance policies intended to mitigate climate change. Two major milestones which have contributed to growing global awareness of this concept include a resolution from the International Labour Organization (ILO) calling for decent work and green jobs in the context of sustainable development,¹⁴ and the Paris Climate Agreements' recognition of the need to support workers while achieving nationally determined GHG reductions.¹⁵ These developments connected the climate crisis to workers' rights on an international stage, while also portraying 'transition' as a process commensurable with economic growth and development. Governments have often emphasized this aspect of just transition, framing it in a way that remains unthreatening to regular capitalist processes of accumulation, and this has increasingly been a point of contention for more radical climate justice organizers.

In June 2023, Canada introduced formal legislation (Bill C-50) to bolster just transition efforts. By May 2024, Bill C-50 had passed through the House of Commons and – as of the time of writing – awaits approval from the Senate.¹⁶ The title of the legislation, initially referred to as a ‘Just Transition Act’, was later swapped for the ‘Sustainable Jobs Act’.¹⁷ This change hints at the strategic impulse underlying the existing federal government’s framing of just transition. The purpose of Bill C-50, officially, is to establish “an accountability, transparency and engagement framework to facilitate and promote economic growth, the creation of sustainable jobs and support for workers and communities in Canada in the shift to a net-zero economy”.¹⁸ In plain language, it is a plan to create institutions that will help with the Liberals’ sustainable jobs agenda.¹⁹

While this proposed legislation is federal in nature, it is evident that Alberta is at the forefront of discussions about just transition. Alberta is responsible for the majority of Canada’s oil and gas production (80% and 63%, respectively), and as a province its carbon emissions have increased by 19% since 2005.²⁰ Moreover, federal legislation affecting oil and gas workers faces barriers in Alberta, including longstanding jurisdictional tension over who has the authority to regulate the province’s energy resources.²¹

In our analysis we categorized four main discourses of just transition, which we labeled ‘Balance’, ‘Worker First’, ‘Transformation’, and ‘Economic Threat’. The foremost

proponent of the Balance discourse is the current Trudeau federal government (though comments by Rachel Notley, the outgoing leader of the official opposition in Alberta, align politically with this interpretation as well). In the simplest sense, this discourse marks an attempt to *balance* climate action, economic growth, and social concerns (including representation for labour, Indigenous organizations, and industry) within Bill C-50. In cautiously striving to advance a climate and jobs agenda that is palatable to a wide base, the Liberals have focused on economic opportunities and expressed a willingness to adopt new terminology: “The global energy transition presents an enormous economic, job-creating opportunity across the country – for those in both conventional and emerging energy and energy related fields. The term ‘sustainable jobs’ is, in our minds, one that is more inclusive and indeed more accurate for Canada than terms like ‘just transition’.”²² Importantly, the Balance discourse envisions a marginally reduced role for oil and gas in a Net Zero economy by 2050, combined with targeted investments in technology and worker retraining.

A similar but distinct discourse – which we call ‘Worker First’ – holds varying goals regarding the rate of decline of oil and gas production, and is less beholden to the specific sector in which the jobs are available, but is unified by its prioritization of concern for workers who stand to be affected. This discourse features some broader justice-related elements (e.g., economic reconciliation with Indigenous nations) which align with labour-focused interpretations of a just transition. However, it is not nearly as

critical as other left interpretations (documented below) in regard to the nature of Canada's contemporary extractive-oriented economy. The Worker First discourse is best encapsulated in a quote by the Alberta Federation of Labour: "If present trends continue, a messy, traumatic, disorderly transition looms, with ordinary Albertans bearing the brunt of the unpleasant consequences. Or Alberta can respond now and design an orderly transition that matches the urgency of the moment".²³ The report "No Worker Left Behind: A Job Creation Strategy for Energy Transition in Alberta" from the Parkland Institute (a non-partisan research group within the University of Alberta) also advocates this Worker First discourse.²⁴ It argues that a workforce transition to a sustainable economy can create over 200,000 new jobs in Alberta by 2050, and simultaneously encourages maintaining a substantial amount of oil and gas extraction (primarily for use in materials manufacturing).²⁵

The third frame we uncovered seeks a radical transformation of Canada's political economy. For such "Transformationalists", a just transition serves as an opportunity to push not only for a rapid phase out of oil and gas production, but also for major changes on interrelated systemic issues that extend beyond fossil fuel workers. A recent case study of this perspective can be found in the book *The End of This World: Climate Justice in So-Called Canada*, which calls for a just transition that encompasses decolonial practices (including "Land Back" advocacy tied to Indigenous Reconciliation) and critiques mainstream interpretations of transition for overlooking

systems-level problems within a growth-based capitalist political economy.²⁶ Workers themselves are not forgotten by Transformationalists. For instance, Alook et al.²⁷ acknowledge that winning support from workers and fossil fuel communities is crucial to a just transition away from fossil fuel production. Similarly, Seth Klein – another prominent Transformationalist – has admonished the Federal Government’s failure “to capture people’s imagination with a compelling counter-offer to all those workers and communities that currently feel economically reliant on fossil fuels.”²⁸ Simply put, those in this discourse coalition would be deeply unsatisfied by the type of transition advocated by the Worker First or Balance discourses, as the latter fail to challenge status quo capitalist relations.

Finally, one increasingly powerful discourse positions just transition as an *economic threat*. Alberta Premier Danielle Smith serves as a vocal champion, but the broader discourse coalition also includes proponents such as Pierre Poilievre, the leader of the Federal Conservative Party, and the Pathways Alliance, an organization comprised of six companies which together operate 95% of Canada’s oil sands production.²⁹ Conservative MP Shannon Stubbs, representing Lakeland, Alberta, is another political spokesperson of this discourse and created an online petition and website entitled Stop Just Transition.³⁰ According to this Economic Threat discourse, Canada can reach net-zero emissions while *expanding* oil and gas production by introducing major technological innovations which enable a carbon neutral subsector.

Therefore, as an exporter of 'clean and ethically produced' energy, Canada has a responsibility to meet global energy demands by continuing to supply petroleum products to those who need them. In this sense, the attempt to transition away from oil and gas is interpreted as an unnecessary economic burden that will "kill 170,000 direct Canadian jobs...and cause major disruptions to 2.7 million jobs".³¹ Premier Smith infamously summarized this perspective with the following Tweet posted alongside a cartoon depicting oil and gas workers being 'transitioned' into Walmart and fast-food employees: "Just Transition!? We have a labour shortage in our oil & gas industry & are growing to meet the world's energy needs. We need more Alberta energy workers...not fewer".³²

As shown in Figure 1, these four discourses do not exist in isolation. Each has some overlapping features with competing discourses. Arguably, how just transition policy in Canada manifests will be the result of how these four discourses, and the actors supporting them, interact within the political sphere.

Figure 1. Summary of the four just transition perspectives with indications of relevant common ground. Developed by authors.

Strategizing for a “Just” Climate-Friendly Future

Smith’s 2023 election victory and the simultaneous policy discussion surrounding the Sustainable Jobs Act represent a crucial juncture in Canadian climate policy, as well as the political relationship between Ottawa and Alberta. Moreover, in the broader political context, Trudeau’s government is currently facing near-record level low polling numbers, largely to the benefit of the Conservatives.³³ Avoiding extreme jurisdictional pushback has become a primary strategic ambition of the current Federal Government as it proceeds with climate-related policies, and this is particularly evident in the framing of Bill C-50. This section further considers the political implications of the interplay between these four Just Transition discourses.

Watering Down of Just Transition

Premier Smith has asserted that she will “not recognize, co-operate with or enforce any attempt to phase out our province’s oil and gas industry or its workforce”.³⁴ While this marks an incompatibility between the Economic Threat and Transformation frames, Smith’s concerns are not necessarily incommensurate with the Liberal Party’s Sustainable Jobs Act. Presently, the Liberals are seeking to appease Smith by incentivizing investments in Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS); indeed, this will be a primary focus of a forthcoming bilateral working group with the Alberta government, a move which has received positive recognition from Smith.³⁵ Moreover, the Federal Government has already started to use different terminology, namely “sustainable jobs,” as a discursive tactic to try to circumvent the political reaction to the very terminology of “just transition”.³⁶ In reality, debates will likely continue regarding jurisdictional issues over energy production, as well as federally imposed emissions caps in the oil and gas sector, as indicated by Smith following her first meeting with Trudeau post-election victory.³⁷

Regarding climate targets, Alberta has stated it is on board with the federal goal of Net Zero by 2050, but has developed its own plan which allows the oil and gas industry to grow while utilizing emissions removal strategies to achieve this ambitious objective.³⁸ Should the Liberals eventually seek to enforce more strict declines in fossil fuel *production* (as opposed to simply targeting *emissions* associated with production),

they will need to contend with the weight of an Alberta provincial government that is strategically aligned with the major industrial players in this field who have little interest in capping production. This was succinctly reinforced by Smith during her recent speech at the Canadian Energy Executive Association conference: “We don't need a just transition in Alberta, because we don't intend to transition away from oil and natural gas...as many of you in the industry have pointed out, the transition we're talking about is a transition away from emissions. It's not a transition away from production.”³⁹

Despite concessions towards the Economic Threat discourse, the Balance discourse has not altogether abandoned some of the progressive ideals of just transition. The inclusion of language around worker and Indigenous representation, and acknowledging barriers faced by equity-seeking groups⁴⁰ may placate, to some degree, the Transformationalist critiques that these important stakeholder voices are being ignored, though it remains to be seen whether such representation will meaningfully influence policy.⁴¹ Moreover, the Federal Government's emphasis on creating sustainable jobs with strong processual representation for unions⁴² marks a smart strategic alliance between the Balance and Worker First priorities by employing a discursive approach to advance their combined visions. Support from organized labour has been strong thus far, as exemplified in a press conference held by NDP MP Charlie Angus and five prominent Canadian labour representatives wherein they expressed

concerns about the Conservative Party delaying the implementation of Bill C-50.⁴³

However, holding the Federal government accountable to the creation of sustainable jobs in a timely and coordinated manner will no doubt remain a challenge for Worker First proponents. For example, the Alberta Federation of Labour has previously expressed concern “that proposals from UCP leadership candidates, like the Alberta Sovereignty Act, will damage policy certainty by creating political chaos.”⁴⁴

One barrier to a coordinated workforce shift is thus the concept of “risk blindness”, which Virla et al.⁴⁵ explored among stakeholders who expect Alberta’s oil and gas sector to grow despite strengthening environmental policies and external market forces. For instance, even with no drastic increase in climate mitigation efforts beyond current practices, global demand for oil is expected to decline before the year 2030, posing potential risks to fossil fuel producing jurisdictions.⁴⁶ As an indication of this global shift, the largest Chinese oil distributor, Sinopec, recently announced that gasoline demand in China is expected to peak this year, two years earlier than previously anticipated, largely due to the availability of electric vehicles.⁴⁷ Whether electric cars are a progressive climate solution is outside the scope of this paper, but nevertheless, dominant institutional narratives such as Smith’s, which emphasize an ever-growing role for Canadian oil and gas production and export, potentially amplify blindness towards these future economic risks for oil and gas producers.

There is therefore a need to overcome risk blindness and justify to afflicted stakeholders why a transition to sustainable jobs is a beneficial path forward for workers and communities. One possibility involves highlighting synergies, or shared benefits such as ameliorating air quality, which can connect global long-term goals to more immediate local benefits.⁴⁸ Another unique approach is to rethink end-use for bitumen such that it is no longer used for combustion downstream, as advocated by the Bitumen Beyond Consumption initiative.⁴⁹ Worker-focussed organizations, such as Iron & Earth, are also working to build public support for a just transition by engaging directly with constituencies who stand to be affected by a decrease in global demand for oil and gas.⁵⁰

As Bill C-50 moves through the process of becoming a law and the government prepares the first Sustainable Jobs Action Plan (set to be released in 2025 and every five years thereafter), different stakeholders will continue to attempt to influence the process of just transition and advance their respective priorities. Given a macroeconomic context where the long-term growth of any fossil fuel is incompatible with any climate mitigation scenario,⁵¹ the Federal Government must avoid further watering down just transition and ensure its 2025 Action Plan prepares Canadian workers for the geo-economic shifts coming down the pike, while also pursuing ambitious climate action through phasing down fossil fuel production – not simply *emissions* reductions.

What's Next for the Transformationalists?

Many of the concerns expressed by the Transformationalist camp are outside the scope of the current Federal Balance discourse, and are often polar opposites of the Economic Threat discourse. Moreover, given current polling numbers, it's likely that Pierre Poilievre will be elected as Prime Minister in the October 2025 election, a result which would immediately shift the Federal discursive approach to transition into alignment with Danielle Smith's anti-transition agenda. Accordingly, there is a strategic debate to be had amongst Transformationalists about how to fight for bold goals given the current political climate in Alberta and Canada. As the Transformationalists have argued, contemporary mainstream approaches to just transition are deeply insufficient from both a climate and a justice perspective. For one, climate and/or transition plans which do not rapidly reduce the production and consumption of fossil fuels, and which instead rely primarily on insufficient and risky investments in CCS,⁵² represent what Transformationalists believe to be a "new climate denialism".⁵³ It is striking that no other discourse seems meaningfully concerned with addressing the issue of fossil fuel *production* declines. Canadian oil and gas production is responsible for 29% of the country's total emissions⁵⁴ - and the sectoral emissions trend is *growing*. Keeping the Transformationalist vision alive is therefore essential if ambitious climate action is to remain on the agenda.

Additionally, the Transformation perspective is particularly effective at emphasizing the interconnectedness of justice issues. This can help discourage siloed thinking when considering how transition policies can have widespread implications on myriad topics beyond workers.⁵⁵ While this more openly radical perspective remains on the fringes of the political discussion, and debates persist on whether (even left-leaning) political parties might be capable of enacting transformative changes, it serves as a powerful vision among grassroots organizations desiring bolder climate action and support for workers and communities.

Indeed, while governments lag behind, resources such as “Don’t Wait for the State: A blueprint for grassroots climate transitions in Canada”⁵⁶ can inspire climate action at the community level and explicitly support workers as part of a transition away from fossil fuel production. Similarly, MacArthur et al.⁵⁷ argue that moving forward with radical transition will require new networks of actors. Cross-movement coalitions, such as labour and environmental alliances, or so-called ‘blue-green coalitions’, serve as one opportunity for further movement building.⁵⁸ Indigenous leadership in a just transition is another crucial aspect of transformative climate justice. For example, as a counterpart to the Sustainable Jobs Act, the organization Indigenous Climate Action co-released a Just Transition Guide which emphasizes that “colonialism, extractivism, and capitalism cause climate change and social injustice” while “Indigenous sovereignty, rights, and leadership create key solutions.”⁵⁹ Indigenous communities are

indeed at the forefront of a transition to renewable energy, but perspectives on future fossil fuel development remain a complex issue often fueled by oil and gas companies “courting Indigenous support”, with some Indigenous leaders “hoping a seat at the table will offer environmental and economic benefits.”⁶⁰ A prominent example is the 2022 agreement between 23 First Nations and Métis communities to acquire 12 percent stake in multiple Enbridge pipelines in Northern Alberta.⁶¹ Although there are evident financial advantages to participating in various resource projects, some Indigenous activists continue to oppose such involvement.⁶² In sum, while the Transformation discourse has been largely absent within government decision-making and policy circles, it has plenty to offer in its insisting on the urgency of the climate crisis and the need for a “‘coordinated movement’ between Indigenous peoples, settler environmentalists, organized labour, and many others.”⁶³

Conclusion

How just transition policy manifests in Canada in the coming years will be the result of the political interplay of different discourses of just transition and their respective proponents. The Sustainable Jobs Act is a manifestation of the current Federal government’s ‘Balance’ approach to just transition. It promises representation for labour stakeholders of the ‘Worker First’ discourse – and simultaneously – concessions towards Alberta Premier Danielle Smith’s ‘Economic Threat’ discourse of just transition.

While this strategic approach may slightly increase the political feasibility of transition efforts in the domestic political sphere, it also risks perpetuating harmful delays in climate action and is deaf to important progressive social policy proposals. This outcome holds implications for more radical 'Transformation' interpretations of transition (involving fossil fuel phase outs and decolonial practices), which have yet to gain much political traction in Canada, but are actively seeking to forge coalitions and build a movement to challenge comparatively weak notions of climate action and justice.

Disclosure Statement

No potential conflicts of interest were reported by either author.

Supplementary Information

Our Supplementary Data Document is available at

<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12550582>

Notes

- ¹ Trudeau, "A Climate Vision That Moves Canada Forward."
- ² Office of the Auditor General of Canada, "Just Transition to a Low-Carbon Economy: Independent Auditor's Report | 2022."
- ³ Thurton, "'Just Transition' Bill Coming in 2023, Natural Resources Minister Says."
- ⁴ Elections Alberta, "Provincial Results."
- ⁵ Government of Canada, "Provincial and Territorial Energy Profiles – Canada."
- ⁶ Smith, "It Has Never Been More Clear...."
- ⁷ Mertins-Kirkwood, "Sustainable Jobs Act: Another Plan to Make a Plan."
- ⁸ Minister of Natural Resources, An Act respecting accountability, transparency and engagement to support the creation of sustainable jobs for workers and economic growth in a net-zero economy.
- ⁹ Forster et al., "Indicators of Global Climate Change 2022."
- ¹⁰ Pineault, "The Capitalist Pressure to Extract."
- ¹¹ Alook et al., The End of This World: Climate Justice in So-Called Canada.
- ¹² Riedy, "Discourse Coalitions for Sustainability Transformations."
- ¹³ Krawchenko and Gordon, "How Do We Manage a Just Transition?"
- ¹⁴ International Labour Organization, "Resolution Concerning Sustainable Development, Decent Work and Green Jobs."
- ¹⁵ United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), "Paris Agreement."
- ¹⁶ Canadian Labour Congress, "Sustainable Jobs Act Passes in House of Commons."
- ¹⁷ Hulse, "Proposals for the Canadian Just Transition Act"; Minister of Natural Resources, An Act respecting accountability, transparency and engagement to support the creation of sustainable jobs for workers and economic growth in a net-zero economy.

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- ¹⁸ Minister of Natural Resources, An Act respecting accountability, transparency and engagement to support the creation of sustainable jobs for workers and economic growth in a net-zero economy.
- ¹⁹ Mertins-Kirkwood, "Sustainable Jobs Act: Another Plan to Make a Plan."
- ²⁰ Government of Canada, "Provincial and Territorial Energy Profiles – Alberta."
- ²¹ Virla et al., "Risk Blindness in Local Perspectives about the Alberta Oil Sands Hinders Canada's Decarbonization"; Muzzerall, "The Cultural Politics of a Just Transition in the Canadian Oil Sands."
- ²² Government of Canada, "Sustainable Jobs Plan."
- ²³ Alberta Federation of Labour, "SKATE TO WHERE THE PUCK IS GOING Re-Imagining Alberta's Energy Future: An Industrial Blueprint for Job Creation and Prosperity."
- ²⁴ Parkland Institute, "New Report Examines Job Creation Plan for a Just Transition in Alberta."
- ²⁵ Ibid.
- ²⁶ Alook et al., The End of This World: Climate Justice in so-Called Canada.
- ²⁷ Ibid.
- ²⁸ Klein, "Long-Awaited Sustainable Jobs Act a Snoozer."
- ²⁹ Pathways Alliance, "Who Are We."
- ³⁰ Stubbs, "Stop Just Transition."
- ³¹ Ibid.
- ³² Smith, "Just Transition!?!?"
- ³³ DeLaire, "Majority of Canadians Not Even Considering Voting for the Liberals: Nanos."
- ³⁴ Aldrich, "'Non-Negotiable': While Ottawa Introduces Sustainable Jobs Act, Premier Smith Stands Her Ground."
- ³⁵ Smith, "I Want to Thank..."
- ³⁶ Rabson, "Federal Government Releases 'Just Transition' Plan to Shift to Clean Energy Economy."
- ³⁷ Smith, "I Want to Thank..."

-
- ³⁸ Government of Alberta, "Alberta Emissions Reduction and Energy Development Plan."
- ³⁹ Bulowski, "Billions in Renewable Investments Stalled as Smith Reiterates Allegiance to Oil and Gas."
- ⁴⁰ Minister of Natural Resources, An Act respecting accountability, transparency and engagement to support the creation of sustainable jobs for workers and economic growth in a net-zero economy.
- ⁴¹ Klein, "Long-Awaited Sustainable Jobs Act a Snoozer"; Mertins-Kirkwood, "Sustainable Jobs Act: Another Plan to Make a Plan."
- ⁴² Minister of Natural Resources, An Act respecting accountability, transparency and engagement to support the creation of sustainable jobs for workers and economic growth in a net-zero economy.
- ⁴³ Cable Public Affairs Channel, "NDP MP Charlie Angus and Unions Discuss Government's Sustainable Jobs Plan – November 2, 2023."
- ⁴⁴ Alberta Federation of Labour, "SKATE TO WHERE THE PUCK IS GOING Re-Imagining Alberta's Energy Future: An Industrial Blueprint for Job Creation and Prosperity."
- ⁴⁵ Virla et al., "Risk Blindness in Local Perspectives about the Alberta Oil Sands Hinders Canada's Decarbonization."
- ⁴⁶ McKenzie, "The Future of Oil in the Energy Transition: Understanding Global Oil Demand Scenarios."
- ⁴⁷ McKerracher, "China Reaches Peak Gasoline in Milestone for Electric Vehicles."
- ⁴⁸ Virla et al., "Risk Blindness in Local Perspectives about the Alberta Oil Sands Hinders Canada's Decarbonization."
- ⁴⁹ Brost, Kern, and Smith, "Electric Vehicle Impact on the Oil Sands."
- ⁵⁰ Iron & Earth, "What We Do."
- ⁵¹ International Energy Agency, "World Energy Outlook 2022."
- ⁵² Cameron and Carter, "Why Carbon Capture and Storage Is Not a Net-Zero Solution for Canada's Oil and Gas Sector."
- ⁵³ Alook et al., The End of This World: Climate Justice in So-Called Canada.

⁵⁴ Canada Energy Regulator, "Canada's Energy Future 2023."

⁵⁵ The Leap, "The Leaf Manifesto"; Alook et al., *The End of This World: Climate Justice in So-Called Canada*.

⁵⁶ Mertins-Kirkwood et al., "Don't Wait for the State: A Blueprint for Grassroots Climate Transitions in Canada."

⁵⁷ MacArthur et al., "Canada's Green New Deal."

⁵⁸ Hess, "Energy Democracy and Social Movements"; Mayer, "Cross-Movement Coalition Formation"; Blue Green Canada, "Resources"; Alook et al., *The End of This World: Climate Justice in so-Called Canada*.

⁵⁹ Sacred Earth Solar et al., "Just Transition Guide: Indigenous-Led Pathways Toward Equitable Climate Solutions and Resiliency in the Climate Crisis."

⁶⁰ Lavoie, "'Nowhere Else to Turn': First Nations Inundated by Oilsands Projects Face Impossible Choices."

⁶¹ Enbridge, "A 'Landmark Collaboration' in Northern Alberta."

⁶² Pasternak, King, Hayden, and Yesno, "Land Back: A Yellowhead Institute Red Paper."

⁶³ Alook et al., *The End of This World: Climate Justice in So-Called Canada*.

References

- Alberta Federation of Labour. "SKATE TO WHERE THE PUCK IS GOING Re-Imagining Alberta's Energy Future: An Industrial Blueprint for Job Creation and Prosperity," October 2022. https://assets.nationbuilder.com/afl/pages/7009/attachments/original/1665103275/Re-imagining_Alberta's_Energy_Future_-_An_Industrial_Blueprint_for_Job_Creation_and_Prosperty_-_Web_-_Final_-_6OCT22.pdf?1665103275.
- Aldrich, Josh. "'Non-Negotiable': While Ottawa Introduces Sustainable Jobs Act, Premier Smith Stands Her Ground." *The Calgary Herald*, June 15, 2023. <https://calgaryherald.com/business/local-business/premier-smith-stands-ground-feds-sustainable-jobs-act>.
- Alook, Angele, Emily Eaton, David Gray-Donald, Joël Laforest, Crystal Lameman, and Bronwen Tucker. *The End of This World: Climate Justice in So-Called Canada*. Toronto, Ontario: Between the Lines, 2023.
- Blue Green Canada. "Resources," 2023. <https://bluegreencanada.ca/resources/>.
- Brost, Ed, Marshall Kern, and Peter Smith. "Electric Vehicle Impact on the Oil Sands." Bowman Centre For Sustainable Energy, June 2020. <https://www.cae-acg.ca/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Electrification-of-Transport-BCSE-July-2020.pdf>.
- Bulowski, Natasha. "Billions in Renewable Investments Stalled as Smith Reiterates Allegiance to Oil and Gas." *National Observer*, August 24, 2023. [https://www.nationalobserver.com/2023/08/24/news/alberta-stalls-33-billion-investments-renewable-energy-pause#:~:text=We%20don%27t%20need%20a,from%20production%2C"%20she%20noted](https://www.nationalobserver.com/2023/08/24/news/alberta-stalls-33-billion-investments-renewable-energy-pause#:~:text=We%20don%27t%20need%20a,from%20production%2C).
- Cable Public Affairs Channel. "NDP MP Charlie Angus and Unions Discuss Government's Sustainable Jobs Plan – November 2, 2023." November 2, 2023. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UOFJAWCySTc&t=965s>.
- Cameron, Laura, and Angela Carter. "Why Carbon Capture and Storage Is Not a Net-Zero Solution for Canada's Oil and Gas Sector." *The Bottom Line*. International Institute for Sustainable Development, February 2023. <https://www.iisd.org/system/files/2023-02/bottom-line-carbon-capture-not-net-zero-solution.pdf>.
- Canada Energy Regulator. "Canada's Energy Future 2023," 2023. <https://www.cer-rec.gc.ca/en/data-analysis/canada-energy-future/2023/canada-energy-futures-2023.pdf>.

-
- Canadian Labour Congress. "Sustainable Jobs Act Passes in House of Commons," April 15, 2024. <https://canadianlabour.ca/sustainable-jobs-act-passes-in-house-of-commons/>.
- DeLaire, Megan. "Majority of Canadians Not Even Considering Voting for the Liberals: Nanos." *CTV News*, March 7, 2024. <https://www.ctvnews.ca/politics/majority-of-canadians-not-even-considering-voting-for-the-liberals-nanos-1.6798245>.
- Elections Alberta. "Provincial Results," 2023. <https://officialresults.elections.ab.ca/orResultsPGE.cfm?EventId=101>.
- Enbridge. "A 'Landmark Collaboration' in Northern Alberta," September 28, 2022. <https://www.enbridge.com/stories/2022/september/landmark-equity-pipeline-partnership-between-enbridge-and-23-indigenous-communities>.
- Forster, Piers M., Christopher J. Smith, Tristram Walsh, William F. Lamb, Robin Lamboll, Mathias Hauser, Aurélien Ribes, et al. "Indicators of Global Climate Change 2022: Annual Update of Large-Scale Indicators of the State of the Climate System and Human Influence." *Earth System Science Data* 15, no. 6 (June 8, 2023): 2295–2327. doi:10.5194/essd-15-2295-2023.
- Government of Alberta. "Alberta Emissions Reduction and Energy Development Plan," April 2023. <https://open.alberta.ca/dataset/7483e660-cd1a-4ded-a09d-82112c2fc6e7/resource/75eec73f-8ba9-40cc-b7f4-cdf335a1bd30/download/epa-emissions-reduction-and-energy-development-plan.pdf>.
- Government of Canada. "Provincial and Territorial Energy Profiles – Alberta," 2023. <https://www.cer-rec.gc.ca/en/data-analysis/energy-markets/provincial-territorial-energy-profiles/provincial-territorial-energy-profiles-alberta.html>.
- . "Provincial and Territorial Energy Profiles – Canada," 2023. <https://www.cer-rec.gc.ca/en/data-analysis/energy-markets/provincial-territorial-energy-profiles/provincial-territorial-energy-profiles-canada.html>.
- . "Sustainable Jobs Plan," March 8, 2023. <https://www.canada.ca/en/services/jobs/training/initiatives/sustainable-jobs/plan.html>.
- Hess, David J. "Energy Democracy and Social Movements: A Multi-Coalition Perspective on the Politics of Sustainability Transitions." *Energy Research & Social Science* 40 (June 2018): 177–89. doi:10.1016/j.erss.2018.01.003.
- Hulse, Matt. "Proposals for the Canadian Just Transition Act." *Ecojustice*, 2023.
- International Energy Agency. "World Energy Outlook 2022," 2022.
- International Labour Organization. "Resolution Concerning Sustainable Development, Decent Work and Green Jobs." General Conference of the International Labour Organization. Geneva, 2013. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_norm/---relconf/documents/meetingdocument/wcms_223785.pdf.

-
- Iron & Earth. "What We Do," n.d. https://www.ironandearth.org/what_we_do.
- Klein, Seth. "Long-Awaited Sustainable Jobs Act a Snoozer." *National Observer*, June 16, 2023. <https://www.nationalobserver.com/2023/06/16/opinion/sustainable-jobs-act-snoozer>.
- Krawchenko, Tamara Antonia, and Megan Gordon. "How Do We Manage a Just Transition? A Comparative Review of National and Regional Just Transition Initiatives." *Sustainability* 13, no. 11 (May 28, 2021): 6070. doi:10.3390/su13116070.
- Lavoie, Judith. "'Nowhere Else to Turn': First Nations Inundated by Oilsands Projects Face Impossible Choices." *The Narwhal*, June 30, 2018. <https://thenarwhal.ca/nowhere-else-turn-first-nations-inundated-oilsands-face-impossible-choices/>.
- MacArthur, Julie L., Christina E. Hoicka, Heather Castleden, Runa Das, and Jenny Lieu. "Canada's Green New Deal: Forging the Socio-Political Foundations of Climate Resilient Infrastructure?" *Energy Research & Social Science* 65 (July 2020): 101442. doi:10.1016/j.erss.2020.101442.
- Mayer, Brian. "Cross-Movement Coalition Formation: Bridging the Labor-Environment Divide*." *Sociological Inquiry* 79, no. 2 (May 2009): 219–39. doi:10.1111/j.1475-682X.2009.00286.x.
- McKenzie, Janetta. "The Future of Oil in the Energy Transition: Understanding Global Oil Demand Scenarios." Pembina Institute, 2022.
- McKerracher, Colin. "China Reaches Peak Gasoline in Milestone for Electric Vehicles." *Bloomberg*, August 29, 2023. <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/newsletters/2023-08-29/china-reaches-peak-gasoline-in-milestone-for-electric-vehicles>.
- Mertins-Kirkwood, Hadrian. "Sustainable Jobs Act: Another Plan to Make a Plan." *The Monitor*, June 22, 2023. https://monitormag.ca/articles/sustainable-jobs-act-another-plan-to-make-a-plan/?utm_source=Shift+Storm&utm_campaign=116e9d260b-EMAIL_CAMPAIGN_2022_12_12_06_32_COPY_01&utm_medium=email&utm_term=0_-498201a42b-%5BLIST_EMAIL_ID%5D&mc_cid=116e9d260b&mc_eid=440418d4af.
- Mertins-Kirkwood, Hadrian, Max Cohen, Isabella Pojuner, and Avi Lewis. "Don't Wait for the State: A Blueprint for Grassroots Climate Transitions in Canada." Canadian Centre for Policy Alternatives, April 4, 2023. <https://policyalternatives.ca/sites/default/files/uploads/publications/National%20Office/2023/04/dont-wait-for-the-state.pdf>.
- Minister of Natural Resources. An Act respecting accountability, transparency and engagement to support the creation of sustainable jobs for workers and

-
- economic growth in a net-zero economy, Pub. L. No. C-50 (2023).
<https://www.parl.ca/DocumentViewer/en/44-1/bill/C-50/first-reading>.
- Muzzerall, Parker. "The Cultural Politics of a Just Transition in the Canadian Oil Sands." Master's Thesis, The University of British Columbia, 2022.
- Office of the Auditor General of Canada. "Just Transition to a Low-Carbon Economy: Independent Auditor's Report | 2022." Reports of the Commissioner of the Environment and Sustainable Development to the Parliament of Canada. Government of Canada, 2022. https://www.oag-bvg.gc.ca/internet/docs/parl_cesd_202204_01_e.pdf.
- Parkland Institute. "New Report Examines Job Creation Plan for a Just Transition in Alberta," February 1, 2023.
https://www.parklandinstitute.ca/media_report_examines_job_creation_plan_for_just_transition.
- Pasternak, Shiri, King, Hayden, and Riley Yesno. "Land Back: A Yellowhead Institute Red Paper." Yellowhead Institute, October 2019.
- Pathways Alliance. "Who Are We," 2023. <https://pathwaysalliance.ca/who-we-are/>.
- Pineault, Éric. "The Capitalist Pressure to Extract: The Ecological and Political Economy of Extreme Oil in Canada." *Studies in Political Economy* 99, no. 2 (May 4, 2018): 130–50. doi:10.1080/07078552.2018.1492063.
- Rabson, Mia. "Federal Government Releases 'Just Transition' Plan to Shift to Clean Energy Economy." *Global News*, February 17, 2023.
<https://globalnews.ca/news/9494850/just-transition-legislation-liberal-federal-government/>.
- Riedy, Chris. "Discourse Coalitions for Sustainability Transformations: Common Ground and Conflict beyond Neoliberalism." *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 45 (August 2020): 100–112. doi:10.1016/j.cosust.2020.09.014.
- Sacred Earth Solar, Indigenous Climate Action, Power to the People, David Suzuki Foundation, and realworld. "Just Transition Guide: Indigenous-Led Pathways Toward Equitable Climate Solutions and Resiliency in the Climate Crisis," 2023.
<https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5c9860bf77b9034bc5e70122/t/6555222edcea4d681ccf0454/1700078320040/Just+Transition+Guide.pdf>.
- Smith, Danielle. "I Want to Thank..." *Twitter*, July 7, 2023.
<https://twitter.com/ABDanielleSmith/status/1677482391835930624>.
- . "It Has Never Been More Clear...." *Twitter*, January 5, 2023.
<https://mobile.twitter.com/ABDanielleSmith/status/1611119725135757317>.
- . "Just Transition!?!..." *Twitter*, January 11, 2023.
<https://mobile.twitter.com/ABDanielleSmith/status/1613214882836647937>.
- Stubbs, Shannon. "Stop Just Transition," 2023. <https://www.stopjusttransition.ca>.

The Leap. "The Leaf Manifesto," September 2015. <https://leapmanifesto.org/wp-content/uploads/Leaplet-digital-NEW.pdf>.

Thurton, David. "'Just Transition' Bill Coming in 2023, Natural Resources Minister Says." *Canadian Broadcasting Corporation*, January 3, 2023. <https://www.cbc.ca/news/politics/wilkinson-just-transition-atlantic-electricity-1.6701409>.

Trudeau, Justin. "A Climate Vision That Moves Canada Forward." *Liberal Party of Canada*, September 24, 2019. <https://liberal.ca/a-climate-vision-that-moves-canada-forward/#0>.

Virla, Luis D., Dirk-Jan van de Ven, Jon Sampedro, Oscar van Vliet, Alistair Smith, Hector Pollitt, and Jenny Lieu. "Risk Blindness in Local Perspectives about the Alberta Oil Sands Hinders Canada's Decarbonization." *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions* 40 (September 2021): 569–85. doi:10.1016/j.eist.2021.10.008.